

DESIGNING FOR SELF-ACTUALIZATION IN CHILDHOOD

Tatiana Mejía Piedrahita
Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering
✉ tatymejia82@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

According to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, self-actualization, which is the motive to realize one's full potential, represents a final level of psychological development. Maslow proposed that, in order to have the ability to self-actualize, an individual needs to fulfil all lower-order (deficiency) needs, such as safety and esteem. Moreover, fulfilling these lower-order needs is a requirement but not a guarantee to reach self-actualization because this requires particular skills and mind-sets. Taking into account that only a small number of adults can reach this level, it seems relevant to explore if and how the ability to self-actualize can be developed and supported from childhood. This paper reports an initial exploration of the question of whether it is possible to design for stimulating self-actualization in children in the context of education. Some key literature is discussed and design directions are proposed.

KEYWORDS: *Self-actualization, Children, Design, Learning environments, Education*

INTRODUCTION

'Human life will never be understood unless its highest aspirations are taken into account.'

(Maslow, 1970, p. XX)

Abraham H. Maslow dedicated his life to the study of people that he considered to be psychologically healthy, an ambition he expressed in his influential book *Towards a Psychology of Being*: 'Indeed, self-actualizing people, those who have come to a high level of maturation, health and self-fulfilment, have so much to teach us that sometimes they seem almost like a different breed of human beings' (Maslow, 1970, p.71). He proposed that human behaviour could be motivated either by deficiency-needs (such as physiological needs and safety needs) or growth-needs (or 'growth values'), and that humans self-actualize when motivated by growth values. Growth values include truth, creativity, beauty, goodness, wholeness, aliveness, uniqueness, justice, simplicity, and self-sufficiency, and are not imposed by religion or culture, but rather naturally developed by healthy human beings:

In addition to Darwinian survival value, we may now also postulate "growth values." Not only is it good to survive, but it is also good (preferred, choices, good for the organism) for the person to grow toward full humanness, towards actualization of potentials, toward greater happiness, serenity, peak experiences, toward transcendence, toward richer and more accurate cognition of reality, and so on. No longer need we rest on sheer viability

and survival as our only ultimate proof that poverty or war or domination or cruelty are bad, rather than good. We can consider them bad because they also degrade the quality of life, of personality, of consciousness, of wisdom (Maslow, 1970, p.61).

The ability to self-actualize is not apparent. Maslow stressed that many people choose the worse rather than the better because growth is often a painful process and may for this reason be shunned; we are profoundly ambivalent about our own best possibilities, both fearing and loving them. He also proposed that one is not born self-actualized: being a human being — in the sense of being born to the human species — must be defined also in terms of becoming a human being: 'In this sense a baby is only potentially a human being, and must grow into humanness in the society and the culture, the family' (Maslow, 1970, p.XXIV). An important challenge, Maslow mentioned, is that growth needs require better outside conditions to make them possible than deficiency needs. As an example, he mentions that *good* environmental conditions are necessary to keep people from killing each other, even *better* conditions to allow people to love each other, and *excellent* conditions are required to make self-actualizing possible.

In this paper, we explore some initial ideas of how design can deliberately contribute to conditions for the self-actualization of children. What kind of 'excellent' conditions can be created and how? This exploration connects to the Positive Design Movement, which explores how design can contribute to human flourishing, as introduced by Desmet and Pohlmeier (2014, p.1): 'Now that human happiness is widely

acknowledged to have an important role in human development, it should be given serious attention in the design discipline as well. It deserves to be examined through scientific investigations and some design research. With design being perhaps one of the most intimate means for reaching people, it is time to explore the possibilities it offers for supporting the inherent human aspiration of living a good life'. Pohlmeier (2012) used positive psychology as a resource to positive design, proposing that design can contribute to user well-being in various fashions (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Design for happiness (Pohlmeier, 2012)

Taking into account that children have yet to develop the ability to self-actualize, their environment, including the social, cultural, and material environment, plays a pivotal role in the establishment of virtues and the development of cognitive, social and emotional skills. In this paper, we first discuss the concept of self-actualization, including the required external conditions. Next, some literature is reviewed that discusses the concept of self-actualization in relation to the development (and education) of children. On the basis of this review, we propose some opportunities to design for self-actualization, including design that supports learning and creativity development.

SELF-ACTUALIZATION

At the basis of Maslow's theory is the proposition that humans are dominated and their behaviour is organized by unsatisfied needs. If a hunter is satisfied, it becomes unimportant in the current dynamics of the individual. The most basic consequence of satiation of any need is that this need is submerged and a new and higher need emerges. The consequence of this is that the human being is a wanting animal and rarely reaches a state of complete satisfaction, except for a short time. As one desire is satisfied, another pops up to take its place. When this is satisfied, still another comes to the foreground, and so on. It is a characteristic of human beings throughout their whole lives that they practically always desire something. The higher the need, the less imperative there is for sheer survival, the longer the need can be postponed, and the easier it is for the need to disappear permanently.

Although influential, Maslow's hierarchy of needs has also been subject to criticism. One important critique is that the proposition that one need has to be satisfied to facilitate the satisfaction of the next one is not supported by empirical evidence. Nonetheless, Maslow's work is considered an important foundation for positive psychology because he was one of the first to study healthy people that have demonstrated the ability to flourish (Seligman et al., 2005).

Self-actualization can be considered to be the need to realize one's potential. It refers to the pursuit of becoming what the individual really is and is capable of being, as Maslow said 'What a man can be, he must be'. What is interesting to mention is that one of the most important and universal characteristics that Maslow found in the subjects he studied and considered as self-actualized, is their creativity. It has been shown that creativity also correlates to other important qualities for being self-actualized, for example spontaneity, non-prejudice thinking, and to enjoy the simplest things, among others (Goble, 1970).

Apart from self-actualization, some authors proposed that there is a significant relationship between creativity and subjective well-being, and this connection results in self-acceptance, personal growth, and a sense of having purpose in life (Taman-aeifar & Motaghedifard, 2014). These authors have found that creative thinking is enhanced by a happy and positive mood, contributing to joy and indirectly to reaching self-actualization through the stimulation of some important values.

CHILDREN AND SELF-ACTUALIZATION

Self-actualized people accept themselves and their life circumstances as they are, feel a harmony in their lives and a fulfillment with all they have; are creative individuals, spontaneous, with a big concern about social issues, and can enjoy and appreciate the simplest things of life (Maslow, 1943). Intuitively, some of these characteristics seem to be present in children. Maslow (as reported in Goble, 1970) actually mentioned that he believed that creativity is one of the important characteristics that people tend to lose when growing up. If that is the case, it is interesting to ask: what are the circumstances in the growing process that causes people to lose their creativity? Or, from a designer's point of view, which design strategies can be used to support and maintain creativity in childhood?

Goble (1970) proposed that the creativity of self-actualized people is similar to children's creativity before they learned to fear the ridicule of others, while they are still able to see things freshly and without prejudice. To be creative it is necessary to be spontaneous, that means being able to express what one is feeling or thinking without any mask. Another important characteristic that is found in self-actualized people and children is the way they can see other people and the world, without any preconceptions, seeing them with uncritical and innocent eyes (Goble, 1970).

Burleson (2005) had found that the good development of children depends on the opportunities available for them to be

exposed to the appropriate stimulation in order to acquire all the abilities necessary for positive physical and mental health, and to become an independent and happy adult. The establishment of virtues, habits and skills in childhood are essential for the brain to create patterns of behaviour that hardly change during an entire lifetime, and that define what is going to happen with the child once he or she becomes an adult (Burlleson, 2005).

UNESCO recognize four pillars of education: (UNESCO)

Figure 2. Pillars of education. Own representation.

According to the report: ‘Learning: the treasure within’, in the section “Learning to be’ they stated: ‘the aim of development is the complete fulfilment of man, in all the richness of his personality, the complexity of his forms of expression and his various commitments — as individual, member of a family and of a community, citizen and producer, inventor of techniques and creative dreamer’ (International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century, Delors & Unesco, 1996)

In this way, education is not solely about acquiring knowledge, but is also about learning how to discover and getting to know one’s self, others, society and, in general, the world. Ensuring that children will have the sufficient resources and opportunities to understand the world, it is expected that they will be able to fit in and become successful people.

Several authors have stated that through learning and creativity, it is possible to encourage children to become self-actualized people (Burlleson, 2005). They stated that creativity, learning and self-actualization constitute a synergistic cycle, where each stage contributes to achieve the others. Table 1 describes the achievements of some of these authors.

Torrance, 1965	Cultivating early experience and belief in personal creativity is a means for a life-long self-actualization, and to have adults with no sense of uselessness about what they do.
Goble, 1970	Children should be enabled to become more and more what they are, understand what they desire to become, and achieve everything they are capable of becoming.
Soloway	Ownership discovery and experimentation, facilitates self-actualization.
Faure, 1972	The task of education is to preserve individual originality, creativity and ingenuity while preparing the individual for a place in real life.

Table 1. Self-actualization in children (Burlleson, 2005)

According to these authors, education and learning environments could support and stimulate the establishment of important foundations in children to become self-actualized adults, through a learning process focused on letting children discover, experiment, and fail, and in so doing cultivate creativity.

DESIGN OPPORTUNITIES

Design is a field of study that aims to develop products and/or services based on most of the case studies of the needs of market consumers. However, it could also be used to create environments and/or experiences able to support and stimulate behaviours and the establishment of virtues and skills. As the learning process in children occurs in their family and educational context, it is important to design these environments in a way that supports happiness, and stimulates creativity and imagination, in order to let children discover who they are, who they want to become, and what their goals, dreams, and expectations are. Also, by applying some design theories to create products that support the values of children and stimulate the acquisition of skills, the production of self-actualized adults is encouraged. Below are exposed some design approaches that were consulted to explore those possibilities within this field.

Persuasive Design

Is defined as all the strategies implemented to try to change, increase, or establish a new behaviour or attitude of people (Fogg, 2003), through the experience and/or use of products, services and environments. Fogg proposed a behavioural model. He states that in order to persuade people it is first of all necessary that they have the motivation, the ability, and the right triggers to show the desired behaviour (Fogg, 2003).

Persuasive design could be used to design learning environments that persuade children to be creative, to explore their world, to know themselves and others, and to support the development of physical, cognitive, emotional, and social skills. It is also important that the design of objects inside those environments encourage children to be curious, to create, and to share with other children. For example, installing rooms inside kindergartens used to create different things using paints, clay, wooden blocks with different shapes, and tools, among

other elements. A place where children could represent themselves, people around them, and the world as they understand it, or just to build whatever they want and imagine.

The design of an education environment that could fit the description of an environment that persuades children to acquire some skills important to promoting self-actualization from childhood, are the kindergartens of 'Buen Comienzo' (the translation in English is 'good beginning') (Municipio de Medellín, s.f.). This is a program in the Municipality of Medellín, Colombia, which gives children from poor neighbourhoods integral attention from pregnancy.

When children are two years old, they work alongside the kindergartens, designed by the Municipality, to achieve the goal of the program: to give children a good education, and in an environment that promotes the well-being and offers the children the same opportunities as those that attend private institutions. The kindergartens have different types of rooms for: sensory stimulation, a theatre, music, playing and learning. With these rooms they promote the creativity, autonomy, freedom, possibilities of expression, and happiness, among other experiences, that are needed to motivate children towards become self-actualized adults.

Figures 3, 4, and 5 present some of the rooms mentioned above (Municipio de Medellín, s.f.). The images show that the rooms have a very simple design and are equipped with different objects and elements to give children the opportunity to imagine and use those elements to create music, a magic world, to interact with other children, to be sociable individuals, and many other activities encouraging their creativity.

Positive design

Another interesting approach of design that could be supportive to make children more self-actualized, is the positive design. It is focused on looking for products that give people a great experience and makes them feel happy (Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013). A happy person is also someone that tends to be more creative, sociable, and energetic, among other characteristics and values that are needed to be a self-actualized person.

Positive design is looking for a way to use the knowledge from positive psychology, which studies the reasons, conditions, and characteristics needed for people to flourish, be happy, and possess good well-being (TU Delft, s.f.). In positive design there are more focused design approaches in a specific area, for example design for happiness, design for subjective well-being, design for emotions and design for virtues. Those could be applied to design products and/or environments for children's development and learning that results in experiences that make them acquire the skills, characteristics, and values needed to stimulate self-actualization in childhood.

These approaches focus more on the possibilities than the problems. Positive design strives to create experiences that make children feel happy, encourages their curiosity, and inspires them to explore their world, their skills and talents; to support the establishment of certain virtues; to know their possibilities and limitations; to accept themselves as they are;

Figure 3. Room of multiple physical activities

to encourage creativity, mingled with the other characteristics that constitute the conditions needed to reach the level of self-actualization.

The most important point is that with the use of those design guidelines it is not necessary to come up with very complicated products. To promote creativity in children and a desire to explore, all that is needed is to develop very simple and flexible ideas (to let children imagine and explore different ways to use it and enjoy it). For example, toys to build as Lego, wooden blocks, a set of magnets, etc.; encourage children to create anything they want and imagine.

With the use of the tools and methodologies of positive design it is possible to develop products that stimulate children to have virtues and to become self-actualized adults, because it takes the knowledge from positive psychology that has studied healthy and flourishing people in order to establish patterns of behaviour, skills and virtues that facilitate the possibility of reaching a self-actualization lifestyle. Moreover, self-actualization as a term introduced by Maslow, who used positive psychology to define it, is totally correlated with the movement of positive design, which makes it easier to justify why those approaches could support self-actualization in children.

It is not possible to think that just with a product or an environment it is possible to give children the opportunity to acquire all the conditions needed to become self-actualized children. For that goal it is necessary that children have access to different ambiances in all the learning contexts that promote happiness, creativity, social contact, an understanding of the world, and the possibility to discover themselves. They also need different products like toys, musical instruments and educational tools, that support the conditions mentioned above.

To explore the opportunities that design could have to contribute in the self-actualization process of children, it is important to mention some specific values, described by Maslow, that are needed to become self-actualized:

- Truth, rather than dishonesty.
- Goodness, rather than evil.

Figure 4. Room sensory stimulation

- Beauty, not ugliness or vulgarity.
- Unity, wholeness, and transcendence of opposites, not arbitrariness or forced choices.
- Aliveness, not deadness or the mechanization of life.
- Uniqueness, not bland uniformity.
- Perfection and necessity, not sloppiness, inconsistency, or accident.
- Completion, rather than incompleteness.
- Justice and order, not injustice and lawlessness.
- Simplicity, not unnecessary complexity.
- Richness, not environmental impoverishment.
- Effortlessness, not strain.
- Playfulness, not grim, humourless, drudgery.
- Self-sufficiency, not dependency.
- Meaningfulness, rather than senselessness.

With the use of the concepts of positive design, and while taking some of the values mentioned above, design could be used as a means to support the values in learning environments giving children the opportunity to have positive experiences, for example:

- Designing games and toys to let children experience the reward obtained when you are honest, with truth you can win. For example, in this point it could be possible to design objects with action-reaction that when children make the right selection, the reaction or feedback from the toy is a reward for them.
- Designing elements to create a theatre, customs, and objects to build different scenarios. With the participation of teachers, children create and represent stories that teach them that when people act evilly, they receive a punishment and are unhappy. It could also be very interesting if children could participate in building the scenarios and creating the customs with guidance, to let them use their imagination and make it tangible.

Figure 5. Music room

- Designing educative objects or toys, to learn in a playful way different concepts that are most of the time boring for children, to demonstrate that everything could be playful and is possible to enjoy while you learn.
- Designing simple play objects to teach children that it is not necessary to have very complex (or very technological) toys and elements to have fun and to be creative. Simplicity is better than complexity. For example, children can entertain themselves with clay and moulds by creating everything that they imagine.
- Designing objects that represent different things from daily living that children must learn to use independently, but which are adequate to their dimensions, and therefore promote exploration in their use, and to learn in a safe way to be self-sufficient in daily activities.
- Designing play objects that allow children to understand that they do not have to fear difference; every person is unique. For example, children that do not have contact with children with disabilities could feel afraid or curious about disability. However, if they have the opportunity to experience it through games they could understand that every individual has different skills and strengths. For example, a game with pirates, in which every player represents a disability (having a wood leg, or an eye patch), and employ different strengths in order to complete tasks.

As the examples mentioned above, positive design, its tools and methodologies, could be used to design learning environments, objects, as well as strategies to support, stimulate, or encourage children to acquire values and skills that are needed in becoming self-actualized adults.

DISCUSSION

Design is about exploring all the possibilities that exist to communicate an intention through the use and experience of products and/or environments. All the approaches mentioned

above give designers some guidelines to focus their efforts and creativity to develop products and/or environments with a goal: to stimulate or motivate children to become self-actualized people. Positive design especially has a lot of potential to support human values, lifestyles, and has a big correlation with self-actualization. Both come from the positive psychology movement, therefore both have the same foundations and principles.

To ensure that children become self-actualized adults, there are different skills, characteristics and values they must gain during their development and growth. In the literature it is possible to find evidence supporting the fact that it is probable to encourage children to be self-actualized human-beings through appropriate stimulus to ensure good development in all the areas and education as a mean, and as an environment to let them explore, learn, and improve their skills and abilities.

The education environment should encourage kids to be creative, know their abilities and talents, give them the opportunity to discover what they like and want, to choose, decide, and fail themselves. Facing failure is really important to make them adults with a tolerance to failure, 'Experts are thus people who have failed many times' (Burlleson, 2005), making them look for more answers and solutions, always searching for a growth in knowledge.

CONCLUSIONS

Taking into account the different perspectives and fields consulted to write this paper, the most important finding is that it is possible to stimulate self-actualization in children applying different methodologies, strategies, and approaches from the design field. Obviously since children's well-being and development also depends on adults around them, it could not be totally assured that just the design of environments and/or products will motivate and support self-actualization. Design is only one of the possible means to achieve this aim.

Designers need to be aware about the influence they can have on someone's life, to apply correctly all the possibilities and tools that exist in this field to obtain products, environments, services and, especially, experiences that support and promote, in this case, the pursuit of self-actualization since childhood.

The findings and connections made in the literature review suggest that design is more than just a knowledgeable area that creates products based on problems, it is also possible to design products or environments that give users positive experiences that, which make them happy. In the case of children, even to help them to become better adults, and with a greater chance of reaching the self-actualization level in their lives. According to the results it is necessary to undertake further research in the field of design for self-actualization, because there is evidence from the psychology and education areas that suggest it is possible to reach this goal.

REFERENCES

- Burlleson, W. (2005) 'Developing creativity, motivations and self-actualization with learning systems', *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 63, page number(s) pp. 436-451.
- Desmet, P. (2012) 'Faces of product pleasure: 25 positive emotions in Human-Product interaction', *International Journal of Design*, VI, page number(s) pp. 1-29.
- Desmet, P., and Pohlmeier, A. (2013) 'Positive design: An introduction to design for subjective well-being', *International Journal of Design*, 7, (3), pp.5-19.
- Faure, E., Herrera, F., Kaddoura, A., Lopes, H., Petrovsky, A., Rahnama, M., and Ward, F. (eds.) (1972) *Learning To Be: The World of Education Today and Tomorrow*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Fogg, B. (2003) *Persuasive Technology*. San Francisco: Morgan Kaufmann Publishers.
- Goble, F. G. (1970) *The third force: The psychology of Abraham Maslow*. Richmond: Maurice Bassett Publishing.
- International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century., Delors, J., and Unesco. (1996). *Learning, the treasure within: Report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty-first Century*. Paris: Unesco Pub.
- Maslow, A. (1943) 'A theory of human motivation', *Psychological review*, 50, pp.370-396.
- Maslow, A. (1970) *Motivation and personality*. 3rd ed., New York: Longman.
- Municipio de Medellín *Micrositio Buen Comienzo. Obtenido de Municipio de Medellín*. Available from: <http://www.medellin.gov.co/irj/portal/ciudadanos?NavigationTarget=navurl://148e1027218a41bc745a2352918af2e>. [access date] Retrieved November 01, 2013 .
- Pohlmeier, A. (2012) 'Design for happiness', *The quarterly magazine of BCS interaction group*, 92, pp.8-11.
- Seligman, M. E., Steen, T. A., Park, N., and Peterson, C. (2005) 'Positive psychology progress. Empirical validation of interventions', *American psychologist*, pp.410-421.
- Soloway, E. (unpublished) *Scaffolded Technology Tools to Promote Teaching and Learning in Science*. Available from: http://hice.org/hiceinformation/papers/misc/scaffolded_technology/index.html. [date accessed].
- Tamannaefair, M. R. and Motaghefidard, M. (2014) 'Subjective well-being and its sub-scales among students: The study of role of creativity and self-efficacy', *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, pp.37-42 .
- Torrance, E.P. (1965) *Rewarding Creative Behavior: Experiments in Classroom Creativity*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.,.
- TU Delft. *Delft Institute of Positive Design*. Available from: <http://studiolab.ide.tudelft.nl/diopd/>.
- UNESCO. *Task force on education for the Twenty-first Century*. Available from: UNESCO: <http://www.unesco.org/delors/ltobe.htm>.